

Advancements in Voting Technology: A Blockchain-Based Review

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Abstract - *Voting is essential to democracy; thus, it must be secure, trustworthy, and transparent. Traditional voting procedures have long been criticized for their inefficiency, lack of security, and lack of transparency. New voting techniques have been created to increase the process's precision, effectiveness, and security. One such decentralized, safe, and unchangeable method is blockchain-based voting. Blockchain-based voting systems record votes in a digital ledger, with each vote encrypted to protect the voter's privacy. Hackers will find it difficult to disrupt the system because the ledger is decentralized and not in the hands of a single body. Since votes cannot be modified after they have been recorded, the immutability of the Blockchain further guarantees the accuracy of the results. This technology makes remote voting possible and can be used to ensure that only authorized voters can cast ballots. However, there are still implementation problems, including ensuring it is secure against cyber attacks and election tampering and a need for standards. More investigation is required to guarantee that the technology is dependable and secure. We will review possible attacks on blockchain, and discuss few solutions.*

Keywords - Blockchain; Ledger; Nodes; Cryptocurrency; proof-of-stake(PoS); proof-of-work(PoW).

1.0 Introduction

1.1 Blockchain

Blockchain technology can be described as a distributed digital ledger system that dispenses the need for a central authority by allowing numerous parties to share and maintain a tamper-proof record of transactions.

It uses encryption to safeguard and validate transactions and depends on a network of computers (called nodes) to keep the ledger's integrity.

Each block creates an immutable record of all transactions in the chain, including a collection of transactions and a different cryptographic hash that connects it to the block before it.

1.2 History

Blockchain technology was first introduced with the rise of digital currencies like Bitcoin. Under the alias "Satoshi Nakamoto," a person or group of persons published a white paper in 2008 that put out the concept of Bitcoin. A decentralized digital currency that could be utilized for safe and transparent transactions without the help of a reliable middleman was suggested in the white paper.

The creation of the Blockchain, a decentralized, distributed ledger, was the major technological advancement underlying Bitcoin. The Blockchain is a growing collection of documents, or blocks, that are connected via encryption. Each block in the chain creates an irrefutable and chronological record of the transactions by including a cryptographic hash value of the block before it.

The Blockchain for Bitcoin was launched for the first time in 2009, and since then, several additional blockchain platforms and protocols have been created. Outside cryptocurrencies, these platforms have been employed in a wide range of applications, including voting systems, healthcare, and supply chain management.

Timeline of the blockchain technology:

- **Year 2008**
 - 08th August: Domain name "bitcoin.org" registered.
 - 31st October: Bitcoin design paper published.
 - 09th November: Bitcoin project registered at SourceForge.net
- **Year 2009**
 - 03rd January: Genesis block established at 18:15:05 GMT
 - 09th January: Bitcoin v0.1 released and announced on the cryptography mailing list
 - 12th January: First Bitcoin transaction, in block 170 from Satoshi to Hal Finney

Nowadays, blockchain technology is viewed as having the potential to revolutionize a number of industries, with advantages including improved efficiency, security, and transparency. The potential

of blockchain technology continues to excite and interest people, despite the technical and regulatory issues that still need to be resolved.

2.0 Applications

The blockchain technology has several uses in a wide range of sectors. The below list includes some of the most popular and promising blockchain applications:

- **Cryptocurrency:** Digital currencies like Bitcoin and Ethereum were created using blockchain technology, which is why it is so well-known. Blockchain technology is used by these currencies to establish a decentralized, open, and secure system of value exchange.
- **Supply chain management system:** Blockchain technology can be used to record the whole supply chain, from raw materials to final goods, in a transparent and secure manner. This can increase productivity, lower expenses, and guarantee the reliability and calibre of goods.
- **Healthcare:** Medical records and patient data management may be done securely and openly using blockchain technology, while maintaining patient privacy.
- **Voting systems:** Blockchain technology can be utilized to build a transparent and secure voting system, thereby lowering the risk of fraud and boosting voter confidence.
- **Digital identity management system:** Blockchain can be used to develop a secure, decentralized system for managing digital identities, potentially lowering the risk of fraud and identity theft.
- **Smart contracts:** Blockchain can be used to establish self-executing contracts that take effect when certain criteria are met. This could possibly eliminate the need for middlemen and boost efficiency.
- **Decentralized finance (DeFi):** Blockchain technology can be used to develop decentralized financial systems that function without the help of conventional financial institutions, possibly enhancing accessibility and cutting costs.

These are only a few of the multiple potential uses for blockchain technology. We are probably going to see a lot more creative use cases emerge as the technology develops and matures. Today, our main topic will be voting systems.

2.1 Why Use Blockchain instead of the existing technologies?

Blockchain technology offers several advantages over traditional technologies, particularly in voting systems. Here are some reasons why using Blockchain for voting might be preferable:

- **Improved Protection:** Blockchain gives improved protection by providing high security and trust. It does so by using cryptography to secure the network. It ensures that the votes cannot be tampered with, manipulated or deleted without any detection, thus reducing the risk of electoral fraud and interference.
- **Transparency:** Blockchain is also transparent as it offers a verifiable system which can be accessed by anyone on the network. Every vote is stored on a public ledger, which is immutable and can also be easily audited. This further helps in maintaining the integrity and accuracy of the results.
- **Decentralization:** As it operates on a decentralized network therefore no centralized authority controls the network. The decentralization reduces the risk of manipulation by an individual party and further improves the system's resilience against cyber-attacks.
- **Accessibility:** A decentralized e-voting system based on Blockchain can make the whole voting process much quicker and accessible to a variety of people, who cannot physically visit the polling stations. This could actually increase the number of voters participating in elections.
- **Expense Efficiency:** Blockchain-based voting systems have the potential to significantly reduce the costs associated with traditional voting systems, such as printing ballots and hiring polling station staff.

Overall, blockchain technology offers a more secure, transparent, and decentralized alternative to existing voting technologies, potentially improving the efficiency, accessibility, and accuracy of the electoral process. Despite all the functionalities, we have some shortcomings, which we will be discussing further.

COMMON ATTACKS

3.1 51% Attack

A 51% attack on a Blockchain-based voting system could be very detrimental, allowing an attacker to manipulate the voting results and undermine the entire system's integrity.

Each vote is recorded as a transaction on the Blockchain. The votes are then validated and confirmed by the network of nodes using a consensus algorithm such as proof-of-work or proof-of-stake. After which, the votes are added to a block and finally, to the Blockchain. This process makes it difficult for anyone to alter or manipulate the vote. However, if an attacker gains over 50% of the network's computing power, they could create a longer chain of blocks and overwrite previous transactions. This control could allow the attacker to reverse or modify the voting results and potentially change the election outcome.

In order to carry out a 51% attack on a Blockchain-based voting system, the attacker must control a significant portion of the network's computing power. It could be achieved by launching a distributed denial-of-service (DDoS) attack on the other nodes of the Blockchain. Protection against a 51% attack can be achieved by increasing the number of nodes on the network. We can also implement a proof-of-stake consensus algorithm, or use a hybrid consensus algorithm that combines proof-of-work and proof-of-stake. Additionally, the voting system could include mechanisms for auditing and verifying the results to detect any potential manipulation.

Our conclusion is that a 51% attack on a Blockchain-based voting system could seriously threaten the integrity and trustworthiness of the system. Therefore, it is crucial to implement robust security measures and constantly monitor and update the system to ensure it remains secure against any potential attacks.

3.2 Sybil Attack

In a Sybil attack, the attacker creates multiple fake identities or nodes to gain control over the network. A Sybil attack can be used in a blockchain-based voting system to create multiple fake identities or nodes and manipulate the voting results in their favour.

A unique id is assigned to each voter, which is used to authenticate them and ensure their vote is valid. Nevertheless, if an attacker somehow creates multiple fake digital ids, they can cast multiple votes, thus manipulating the voting results in their favour.

Several measures can be taken to prevent a Sybil attack in a blockchain-based voting system. One approach is to use a proof-of-work (PoW) mechanism, where each node in the network must solve a complex computational puzzle before it can participate in the network. This mechanism makes it difficult for an attacker to create multiple fake identities, requiring significant computational power. Another approach is to use a proof-of-stake (PoS) mechanism, where each node in the network must hold a certain amount of Cryptocurrency to partake in the network. Therefore, the PoS mechanism makes creating multiple fake identities costly for an attacker, as it would require a significant Cryptocurrency investment.

In addition to these measures, it is essential to implement robust identity verification protocols to ensure that each voter is unique and authenticated. Additional measures can include biometric verification or other forms of identity verification to ensure each vote is valid and legitimate.

3.3 DDoS Attack

DDoS (Distributed Denial of Service) is a cyber-attack where an attacker overwhelms a target computer system with a surge of traffic from multiple sources, causing it to become inaccessible or slow down significantly. Regarding blockchain-based e-voting systems, a DDoS attack can have serious consequences.

In a blockchain-based e-voting system, voters vote using digital tokens recorded on a decentralized ledger (Blockchain). This allows for a transparent and secure voting process resistant to fraud and manipulation. However, if an attacker launches a DDoS attack on the blockchain network, they can disrupt the voting process and compromise its integrity.

Here is how a DDoS attack on a blockchain-based e-voting system might work:

- The attacker identifies the blockchain network that the e-voting system is built on.
- They use a botnet (a network of compromised computers) to send a flood of traffic to the network, overwhelming its capacity and causing it to slow down or crash.
- As a result, voters cannot cast their votes or access the system, causing chaos and confusion.
- The attacker may also use this opportunity to manipulate the blockchain ledger and alter the voting results since the network cannot keep up with the flood of traffic.

To mitigate the threat of a DDoS attack on a blockchain-based e-voting system, security measures should be implemented to detect and prevent such attacks. These measures may include:

- Implementing firewalls and intrusion detection systems to detect and block suspicious traffic.
- Distributing the blockchain network across multiple nodes prevents a single point of failure.
- Implementing rate limiting to prevent a flood of traffic from overwhelming the network.
- Using consensus algorithms to ensure that multiple nodes validate any changes to the blockchain ledger before being accepted.

In conclusion, a DDoS attack on a blockchain-based e-voting system can compromise the integrity of the voting process and undermine democracy. It is important to implement it robustly.

4.0 Conclusion And Future Work

This paper discusses a new emerging voting technology that can potentially change how we vote. It might seem like a utopia now, but so did making payments online with one tap on our phones. Technology is rapidly evolving, and it's time we implement them and improve our lives. We hope that our paper was able to explain the possibility of a new voting system, -what its shortcomings are and how to overcome them.

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